

945358-BIGPICTURE Central Repository for Digital Pathology

WP1 - Project management and dissemination

D1.05 Project Website

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Document History

Version	Date	Author	Changes
0.1	22-11-21	Estelle Chanudet-van den Brink	First Draft based on H2020 template
0.2	29-11-21	Jeroen van der Laak and Anna-Lena Frisk	Textual edits, additions
0.3	06-12-21	Project Management Office	Review and finalization layout
1.0	15-12-2021	Managing Board Review	Review
1.1	16-12-2021	Final report	Finalization after input

Abstract

One of the main objectives of the BIGPICTURE project is to engage, at a Europe-wide scale, stakeholders as diverse as pathologists, AI-scientists, pharmaceutical companies, healthcare policy makers, regulators and SME's. Reaching such a diverse audience is a major challenge, which requires to delineate and maintain a common understanding among all involved partners, and deliver, with a single voice and in an adequate format, a clear message on what we are doing, why and how.

For this purpose, BIGPICTURE partners have worked together to develop and launch a public project website (<https://www.bigpicture.eu/>): the objectives and targeted audience were defined first; a structure was then specified and implemented through a pre-release version, finalized after internal review.

This resulted in a multi-page website organized around a concise menu and a strong visual elements component emphasizing the project's goals, its organization and its vision for the future. This website is our 'front door' for the outside world, aiming it to be as informative, representative and attractive as possible to keep all involved stakeholders engaged and widen the community throughout the project duration and beyond.

Methods

As per Task 1.4 ("In parallel [to delineating the communication strategy (D1.03)], the project website will be set up, paving the way for an effective PR strategy and of the project, relevant for future sustainability of the developed infrastructure), the website structure was drafted by BIGPICTURE Work Package 1. Multiple rounds of discussion were set up, respectively focusing on the project website objectives, the expectations of the targeted audience, how to adequately represent the diversity of stakeholders, and the alignment of key messages as per the Dissemination Communication and Exploitation Plan (DCEP; deliverable D1.03). As an outcome, specifications were defined, along with a draft structure. The website structure was produced in collaboration with Betawerk, an accomplished website builder with ample experience in the field of research and technology. The professional house-style, developed alongside the DCEP was implemented to provide a recognizable and attractive visual identity, stressing our infrastructure's leitmotiv description as an inclusive and trustworthy endeavour. The development of the website content management system and the implementation of the house-style were achieved in close consultation with WP1, by organizing multiple online discussion sessions with the service providers.

Textual and graphical content for the website was provided by WP1, the Managing Board, as well as all Work Package and Task Force leaders, on behalf of their BIGPICTURE collaborators, so that the website would adequately represent all partners involved. Particular attention was given to translate the complexity of the project into a lay language while remaining precise and focussing attention to key elements such as BIGPICTURE's mission, its vision, the way the project is organized, and the projects' progress and impact.

Replacing the primary landing page launched on 30th of July 2021, a more elaborated version of the website will be live by end of December 2021. The website will be maintained by WP1, with the support of Betawerk. The website will continuously be updated to contain timely information regarding news, events and project progress. In addition, in the coming months the website content will be gradually enriched and further harmonized. Towards the medium term of the project, the structure of the website will evolve to contain sections that specifically target the audiences identified during the development of the sustainability strategy by WP6. The website will thus become part of the tool box dedicated to develop BIGPICTURE's network of contributors, users and founders.

Results

The newly developed BIGPICTURE public website, launched on 21st December, is available via the following weblink: <https://www.bigpicture.eu/>. The underlying strategy, targeted audiences and key messages are further described in the coupled deliverable D1.03 (Dissemination Communication and Exploitation Plan, DCEP).

In brief, the website specifications were set as followed:

- Definition: the BIGPICTURE website is a public website containing project-related information in an accessible and user-friendly format.
- Supporting technology: The website was built and will remain securely hosted and regularly maintained by Betawerk, a website builder specialized in research and technology websites, ISO27001 (information security) and NEN7510 (health information) certified. It is running on Drupal Content Management System to smooth the uploading, publishing and editing of content. It is infinitely scalable and all source code will fully be transferred at the end of the collaboration. All website content is stored within the EU, in a GDPR compliant manner.
- Policy: Website content will strictly follow BIGPICTURE Standard Operating Procedures on Communication and Dissemination and BIGPICTURE Publication and Authorship policy (annexed to D1.03 DCEP), which are compliant with IMI guidance on communication and results' dissemination.
- Design: The visual concept for the website was defined as part of the communication strategy by the external professional designer who developed the BIGPICTURE house-style, in close collaboration with Betawerk designers. Notable key elements include:
 - o the colour scheme, inspired by the hematoxylin and eosin dyes: this is the principal staining routinely applied to histological sections for the pathologist to differentiate the different components of examined tissues;
 - o Rectangular shapes following the proportions of the glass-slides on which histological sections are typically mounted to allow examination under the pathologists' microscope.
- Primary audience: the website is the main interface of the BIGPICTURE project with the general public, including (but not limited to) all stakeholders with an interest in pathology, artificial intelligence, ethical and legal aspects of clinical data sharing, and, more generally, healthcare breakthroughs from the clinicians, researchers and patients' perspectives.
- Primary objectives: this website first aims to raise the profile of BIGPICTURE among the general public by providing a fully open online interface to describe who we are, what we do and why. It will keep the BIGPICTURE community spirit alive and ultimately will be supporting the expansion of the community.

As for the content, the landing page itself offers a sharp description of our goals and expected impact, together with a direct access to most recent highlights and our contact details. The concise menu offer the possibility to navigate through the following items:

1. About us: What is Bigpicture about, Mission & Vision, Governance
2. Our Work: Objectives, Strategy and Impact
3. Our Team: Participants, Structure, Network

News and FAQ sections are also directly available from the main menu.

Overall, the key highlights of this public website are:

- An accessible description of who we are and why our work is essential:

Mission & Vision

[Home](#) › [About us](#) › [Mission & Vision](#)

Our mission

BIGPICTURE will set up the first European, ethical- and General Data Protection Regulation-compliant, quality-controlled and community-based platform, in which both large-scale data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms will coexist.

Pathologists traditionally examine body tissues on a glass slide under a microscope, an essential step to precisely diagnose diseases and guide treatment options. Scanned glass slides are now opening the way to digital image analyses.

While artificial intelligence is enabling computer systems to perform more and more complex tasks, the access to large-scale adequate pathology images to efficiently train AI algorithms is still a rate limiting step for AI-supported pathology.

Our Vision

BIGPICTURE's vision is to become the catalyst in the digital transformation of Pathology.

Artificial intelligence is pathology next big thing

The development of AI in Pathology will accelerate the discovery and validation of biomarkers to better understand, diagnose and predict diseases. It will also improve both the quality and efficiency of toxicity studies and in turn, boost drug development for the benefit of patients.

- An easy-access to the list of all involved partners:

- An explanation of our structure and approach, including engaging storylines:

‘AI is still in its infancy’

‘AI is still in its infancy, but will have a big role in the future in supporting the specialists with diagnostics and treatment options’ says Jeroen van der Laak. The development of AI relies on data, which is not easy to come by. Besides, there are legal and ethical requirements to take into account regarding the safety and privacy of patients’ data. BIGPICTURE has set a goal of gathering 3 million images for its repository. It should be a variety of images on all sorts of body tissues and disease as well as animal tissues from non-clinical studies to make sure AI algorithms can be as widely applicable and accurate as possible. ‘A heterogenic dataset will ensure that algorithms can be used on a larger scale, and this is what we really want to pursue with BIGPICTURE.’

- A series of key figures that will evolve to actively show our progress at one glance:

- The latest news and highlights including publications, press-releases and other project’s outcomes to support the dissemination of our results and their impact, with dynamic content that can be displayed chronologically:

LATEST NEWS

<p>29 August, 2021</p> <p>Computational Pathology Symposium</p> <p>The sixth edition of the Computational Pathology Symposium was held on August 29, 2021, in conjunction with...</p> <p>Read more</p>		
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[View all news](#)

- A list of Frequently Asked Questions to reach out to the general public:

FAQ

[Home](#) › [FAQ](#)

Is the BIGPICTURE initiative GDPR-compliant?	+
How is the BIGPICTURE project funded?	+
What is the role of the pharmaceutical industry in the BIGPICTURE project?	+
How will my data privacy be ensured with all these different partners and countries involved?	+
Who will have access to the collection?	+
Why do you need so many partners?	+
Who is checking whether my data is used in a sensible way?	+
How big will BIGPICTURE collection be?	+
Does this mean my biopsies are not going to be seen by a doctor?	+

This website will also ensure a direct subscription link to our newsletter when the first issue will be released. Similarly, the calendar of coming events/workshops/meetings/training of high interest for our community will be regularly updated, and will include information about the targeted audience and registration link as appropriate.

To smooth further the navigation, a search tool is accessible from the top menu and links are redirecting the visitors to our own contact page and social media network (including LinkedIn for now, to be expanded as applicable), but also key related websites, including IMI and BIGPICTURE's key related networks such as the Grand Challenge organization. Funding acknowledgement and disclaimer are directly accessible from every page via dedicated footer sections.

Disclaimer and privacy statement

[Home](#)

Disclaimer

This website reflects the author's view and neither IMI nor the European Union, EFPIA or any Associated Partners are liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Privacy Statement

The protection of your data is of particular concern to us. We process your data in accordance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). With the help of this data protection declaration, we inform you comprehensively about the processing of your personal data and the rights to which you are entitled.

Personal data is the information that makes it possible to identify a natural person. This includes in particular your name, date of birth, address, telephone number, e-mail address and your IP address.

Finally, built-in open-source monitoring tools accessible to the project management team to monitor website traffic: Matomo Web analytics (GDPR compliant European alternative for Google Analytics) to quarterly evaluate the visits to the BIGPICTURE website in terms of number of (new or returning) visitors, number of pages viewed, average time spent etc.

Discussion

There are no deviations from the DoA.

Conclusion

The BIGPICTURE public website provides accessible information on who we are and how we are transforming the future of pathology by the development of AI solutions. This website is at the heart of the projects' community building efforts and will pave the way to an effective public relations strategy.

While strengthening our internal engagement as a booming community, the website aims to grow into a key component to achieve our goal of creating a BIGPICTURE community which far exceeds the BIGPICTURE project partners. This website will evolve along with the project with the ultimate objective to help attracting new contributors, thus actively contributing to the sustainability of the infrastructure and the expansion of its impact.